

EARTH SCIENCES

STRUCTURAL GROUP ANALYSIS OF OILS AT VARIOUS HEAT TREATMENT PROCESSES BY ^{13}C NMR SPECTROSCOPY

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Abstract

Application of high resolution ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy to characterize of oils at various heat treatment processes was demonstrated. Molar fractions of aliphatic, aromatic, C=O, C-O, C=C carbon groups of four oil samples according to ^{13}C NMR spectra were determined. The received parameters indicate about the success of the heat treatment processes for studied oils.

Keywords: ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy; oil; functional group; qualitative analysis; quantitative composition; heat treatment.

1. Introduction

^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has recently become increasingly popular as a tool for studying the characteristics of natural raw materials and their individual organic compounds ([1]; [2]; [3, 6942-6946]; [4, 1-9]; [5, 2858-2864]; [6, 117622]; [7, 597-598]). NMR spectroscopy is used to study various petrochemical objects, expanding the possibilities for research in the field of geological and chemical problems ([8, 423-473]; [9]). There are some important advantages regarding this analytical technique ([10, 464-475]; [11, 18-37]).

NMR has been also used in the analysis of heavy petroleum fractions in many researches ([12, 280-281]; [13, 111-120]; Bansal et al., 1998 [14, 1223-1227]; [15, 81-86]; [16, 151-123]). The main purpose was to help refineries to refine heavy crude oils more efficiently and at low processing costs.

The advantages of NMR spectroscopy are a reduction in the time taken for the analysis, and that it is a rapid and non-invasive process. Moreover, by using NMR, it is possible to analyze the chemical nature of individual types of hydrogen and carbon atoms, in various and complex mixtures of petroleum and in the final products obtained by refining processes. In the NMR spectra, the functional groups of aromatics, aliphatics, and olefins can be fixed; accordingly, it is possible to differentiate a polynuclear aromatic from a mononuclear aromatic and to identify the fuel physical properties by the concentration of aromatics and the chain length of aliphatics. The suitable information about the molecular carbon skeleton can be obtained by ^{13}C NMR. This NMR technique is important for the structure elucidation and chemical composition of a sample. In addition, it distinguishes the existence of quaternary

carbons of many functional groups, and produces spectra with well quality. For this reason, ^{13}C NMR has become one of the most important methods in the analysis of crude oil fractions.

The objective of this work is to be carried out the comparison between original, first combustion, second combustion (thermal steam effect), third combustion (in air) oil samples by analyzing their structural-group characteristics from ^{13}C NMR spectra.

2. Materials and methods

NMR experiments on studied oil samples were performed on a Bruker Avance III HD 700 NMR spectrometer. The studied oil sample was diluted with deuterated chloroform. Field lock and shimming were achieved using the deuterium signal from CDCl_3 solvent.

^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using 90° pulses with broadband proton decoupling (pulse program zgig); relaxation delay between consecutive accumulations were 3.3 s (and acquisition time was 2.3 s); spectrum width was set to 220.0 ppm; number of scans was 1300. Exponential digital filter with the LB parameter of 10 Hz was applied prior to Fourier transformation. Measurements were made at the temperature of 25°C . All the NMR spectra were integrated after baseline correction, and a mean of minimum three integration values has been taken for each calculation. The relative standard deviation of the results of manual integration did not exceed 3%.

3. Structural-group characterization and comparison of oils at various heat treatment processes by high resolution ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

The structural-group analysis method with the data obtained from analysis the ^{13}C NMR spectra to determine the oil composition can be used (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts of functional groups defining the composition of oil samples [17].

^{13}C NMR chemical shifts range, ppm	Organic functional group
11.0–12.5	γ - CH_3 -groups and some CH - and CH_2 - groups in aromatic fragments, CH_3 - group in ethyl-substituted cyclohexane
12.5–15.0	γ - CH_3 - (and more distant) methyl groups of aromatic cycle; CH_3 - group, shielded by two neighboring aromatic rings
15.0–18.0	β - CH_3 - substituent in ethylene group
18.0–20.5	α - CH_3 - group, shielded by one aromatic; some α - CH_3 - and CH_2 - groups in hydroaromatic and naphthenic fragments
20.5–22.5	α - CH_3 - group, unshielded by aromatic; some α - CH_3 - and CH_2 - groups in hydroaromatic and naphthenic fragments
22.5–24.0	γ - CH_2 - and CH_3 -groups; β - CH_2 - groups in unsubstituted tetralin structures
24.0–27.5	methylene (CH_2) groups in naphthenic fragments; α - CH - and β - CH_2 - groups in a propyl and indan fragments; β - CH_3 - group in isopropyl
27.5–37.0	methylene (CH_2) groups, do not neighboring with methine (CH) group in alkyl compounds; methylene (CH_2) group in cycle
37.0–60.0	methine (CH) group in alkyl fragments; CH and CH_2 alkyl groups of naphthenic fragments, adjacent to CH group
108.0–118.0	olefin fragments
118.0–129.5	protonated arenes
129.5–133.0	internal aromatic carbon atoms
133.0–135.0	methyl substituted arenes
135.0–138.0	arenes, substituted by naphthenes
138.0–160.0	alkyl substituted (except for methyl substituted) arenes; heteroatomic (N, O, S) arenes
165.0–175.0	ester or amide carboxy carbon atom
170.0–182.0	acid carboxy carbon atom
182.0–192.0	quinone carboxy carbon atom
195.0–205.0	aldehyde carbonyl carbon atom
202.0–220.0	ketone carbonyl carbon atom

Information obtained by integration of aliphatic, aromatic, $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{C}$ carbon groups signals in individual spectral ranges is represented by the fraction of the corresponding carbon atoms relative to their total number. For example, the fraction of aromatic carbons C_{ar} can be straightforwardly found from NMR spectra:

$$C_{ar} = \frac{I_{ar}}{\sum_j I_j}, \quad (1)$$

where C_{ar} is the fraction of aromatic carbons, I_{ar} is the total integral intensity of aromatic carbons, and I_j is the integral intensity of all functional groups in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the sample.

The estimation of molar fractions of aliphatic and aromatic carbon groups by integration of the corresponding areas of ^{13}C NMR spectra we have already done before in our previous works ([18, 12-18]; [19, 256-262]; [20, 995]; [21, 8-12]). In this work, the estimation of molar fractions of $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{C}$ were added, since these data are very important for studied oils obtained after combustion processes (Table 2).

Table 2.

Molar fractions (%) of aliphatic (C_{al}), aromatic (C_{ar}), $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{C}$ carbon groups of oil samples at various heat treatment processes based on ^{13}C NMR spectra.

Group type	Relative molar content, %			
	original	combustion 1	combustion 2 (steam)	combustion 3 (air)
C_{al}	40.1	42.3	45.5	36.3
C_{ar}	27.5	26.4	25.3	28.6
$\text{C}=\text{O}$	0.2	1.8	1.6	2.4
$\text{C}-\text{O}$	1.1	2.7	2.4	3.1
$\text{C}=\text{C}$	25.4	26.8	25.2	29.6

Based on obtained data (Table 2), we can see that the maximum concentration of $\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ groups is observed for oils obtained after the combustion 3 process (in air), and their minimum concentration

is for oil samples after the combustion 2 (in steam). Considering also the C_{al} and C_{ar} parameters we can conclude that a noticeable effect on oil upgrading occurs

for oil after the combustion 2 (maximum of C_{al} and minimum of C_{ar}). This is a consequence of the smoother processes of destruction of high-molecular components, cleavage of side chains (C-O, C-S) and destructive hydrogenation with cleavage of C-S-C bonds in the oil after the combustion 2. Thus, using the ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, it is possible to prove that the use of heat treatment with thermal steam effect is most effective for upgrading oil and improving the quality of fuel.

4. Conclusions

The structural-group characteristics of four oil samples (original, first combustion, second combustion (thermal steam effect), third combustion (in air)) were obtained from ^{13}C NMR spectra analysis. As a result of the analysis of the C_{al} , C_{ar} , C=O, C-O, C=C parameters obtained from the data of ^{13}C NMR spectra, it was established that the process of combustion 2 with thermal steam effect is more preferable for oil upgrading.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation under agreement № 075-15-2022-299 within the framework of the development program for a world-class Research Center “Efficient development of the global liquid hydrocarbon reserves.”

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